

APPLICATION OF BEER'S LAW OF ABSORPTION TO SOLUTIONS.

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Application of Beer's law to the solutions of potassium dichromate, picric acid, didymium nitrate, methyl violet, methylene blue, chromic acid, nickel nitrate, nickel sulphate, nickel chloride and cobalt chloride has been tested. It is observed that nickel chloride and cobalt chloride behave similarly to cupric chloride and does not obey Beer's law. While solutions of other substances follow the law more or less approximately, deviation being greater as the concentrations become widely separated. The results also indicate that ionisation alone is not responsible for deviation from Beer's law.

According to Beer's law when an absorbing substance is in the gaseous state or dissolved in a transparent solvent, the absorption coefficient is proportional to the concentration. Thus $e = k c$.

It is well known that the law is valid only in case of monochromatic radiations and when the molecular characteristic of the dissolved substance does not change with dilution. The law does not hold good in the case of cupric chloride solution due to the formation of complex ions. Thus :—

However, the law is applicable in case of potassium permanganate and others (*cf.* Dhar, "Chemical Action of Light", p. 17).

In this paper an attempt has been made to investigate the applicability of this law to various solutions in various regions of the visible spectrum. The amount of absorption and extinction coefficients for different concentrations were determined with the help of Nuttings photometer combined with constant deviation spectrometer. The regions compared were not strictly monochromatic due to the width of the slit of the telescope, although they were identical for all solutions. The width of the region was about $200\text{\AA}$. The observed results together with those calculated on the basis of proportionality between e and c are given below. It is assumed that the observed values for the lowest concentrations are the true values and on this basis expected values at other concentrations are calculated. This principle is separately followed in each table.

The thickness of the solution in all cases was 1 cm. Concentrations were expressed either as mols per litre or number of grams in a given volume or in terms of normality = $\frac{\text{Molecular weight}}{\text{Basicity of the salt}}$. e = observed extinction coefficient, e_c = calculated value of extinction coefficient. l = wave length in Å units.

TABLE I.

		<i>Potassium dichromate.</i>				
Conc.		5400Å.	5500Å	5600Å	5800Å.	6000Å.
0'0513 M	e	0'25	0'10	—	0'04	0'02
"	e_c	0'25	0'10	—	0'04	0'02
0'256	e	1'32	0'52	0'20	—	—
"	e_c	1'25	0'50	0'20	—	—
0'513	e	2'8	1'06	0'40	0'14	0'04
"	e_c	2'5	1'00	0'40	0'40	0'20

It appears from these results that in regions where absorption is appreciable ($\lambda = 5400\text{Å}$, 5500Å and 5600Å) Beer's law is more or less applicable for all the concentrations examined. When, however, the extinction coefficient becomes small ($\lambda = 5800\text{Å}$ and 6000Å) the law is not valid. It is to be further observed that the deviation becomes more marked as the concentrations differ more and more from one another. Thus the results when 0'256 M and 0'513 M solutions of potassium dichromate are alone compared are in better agreement than when all the solutions are compared together. This is obvious, because when change in concentration is small, the deviation is also small.

TABLE II.

		<i>Picric acid.</i>		
Conc. (g./100 c.c.)		4850Å.	5000Å.	5180Å.
0'666	e	0'60	0'09	0'03
"	e_c	0'60	0'09	0'03
1'333	e	1'05	0'17	0'07
"	e_c	1'20	0'18	0'06

For the concentrations examined the Beer's law seems to be applicable in cases of picric acid.

TABLE III.

Didymium nitrate.

Conc. (g./100 c.c.)		4370Å.	4400Å.	4470Å.	4590Å.		
22'687	<i>e</i>	0'19	0'19	0'21	0'32		
"	<i>e.</i>	0'19	0'64	0'21	0'32		
45'375	<i>e.</i>	0'35	1'19	0'40	0'58		
"	<i>e.</i>	0'38	1'28	0'42	0'67		
		4640Å.	4720Å.	4850Å.	5000Å.	5020Å.	
22'687	<i>e</i>	0'41	0'26	0'05	0'47	0'50	
"	<i>e.</i>	0'41	0'26	0'05	0'47	0'50	
45'375	<i>e</i>	0'72	0'49	0'07	0'79	1'03	
"	<i>e.</i>	0'82	0'52	0'10	0'94	1'00	
		5100Å.	5180Å.	5380Å.	5640Å.	5870Å.	6540Å.
22'678	<i>e</i>	0'74	0'29	0'04	1'65	0'02	0'11
"	<i>e.</i>	0'74	0'29	0'04	1'65	0'02	0'11
45'375	<i>e</i>	1'27	0'57	0'07	2'25	0'03	0'18
"	<i>e.</i>	1'48	0'58	0'08	3'30	0'04	0'22

The absorption by didymium nitrate is known to be peculiar. It shows various regions of maximum absorptions (*cf.* Bhagwat and Dhar, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1931, **35**, 2393), the centres of maxima being near about 4200 Å, 4640 Å, 5000 Å, 5020 Å, 5100 Å, 5640 Å and 6540 Å. The above results point out that Beer's law is more valid in regions other than those of maximum absorption.

The absorption of didymium nitrate at lower concentration has also been determined, but when the results are calculated on this basis the deviation from Beer's law is much marked. In other words, the deviation from Beer's law becomes more pronounced as the difference in concentration increases.

TABLE IV.

Conc. (g./100 c.c.)		4370Å.	4470Å.	4590Å.	4720Å.	4850Å.	5000Å.	5180Å.	5640Å.	6540Å.
4.5375	<i>e</i>	0.05	0.05	0.07	0.06	0.02	0.10	0.07	0.40	0.03
"	<i>e.</i>	0.05	0.05	0.07	0.06	0.02	0.10	0.07	0.40	0.03
22.687	<i>e</i>	0.19	0.21	0.32	0.26	0.05	0.47	0.29	1.65	0.11
"	<i>e.</i>	0.25	0.25	0.35	0.36	0.10	0.50	0.35	2.00	0.15
45.375	<i>e</i>	0.35	0.40	0.58	0.49	0.07	0.79	0.57	2.25	0.18
"	<i>e.</i>	0.50	0.50	0.70	0.60	0.20	1.00	0.70	4.00	0.30

The results clearly show that the deviation from Beer's law is appreciable for the higher concentrations (45.375 g.) than for the concentration (22.687). Beer's law therefore is not valid in this case when the concentrations compared are widely apart. It is to be further observed that this deviation is much greater in the regions where absorption is very low and also very high.

TABLE V.

Methyl violet.

Conc. (g./100 c.c.)		6540Å.	6160Å.	4850Å.	4720Å.	4590Å.	4470Å.	4370Å.	4280Å.
0.0020	<i>e</i>	—	0.09	0.27	0.19	0.14	0.12	0.12	—
0.010	<i>e</i>	0.03	0.44	2.00	1.32	0.76	0.52	0.35	—
0.025	<i>e</i>	0.07	0.80	—	1.85	1.85	1.12	0.75	0.50
0.050	<i>e</i>	0.12	1.50	—	—	—	1.85	1.22	0.76
0.100	<i>e</i>	0.23	—	—	—	—	—	1.95	1.5

It seems that Beer's law is not applicable in the case of methyl violet solutions. The law is not approximately valid even when the absorption of similar concentrations, such as 0.050 and 0.100 g. in 100 c.c. or 0.025 g. and 0.050 g. in 100 c.c. are compared with one another. In view of the fact that these dyes behave as colloids the deviation from Beer's law at high dilutions is as expected, since the molecular complexity changes with dilution.

TABLE VI.

Methylene blue.

Conc. (g./100 c.c.)		5380Å.	5180Å.	5000Å.	4850Å.	4720Å.	4590Å.	4470Å.
0.0116	<i>e</i>	1.46	1.08	0.86	0.72	0.54	0.34	0.27
"	<i>e.</i>	1.46	1.08	0.86	0.72	0.54	0.34	0.27
0.0232	<i>e</i>	2.6	2.05	1.70	1.38	1.04	0.84	0.66
"	<i>e.</i>	2.92	2.16	1.72	1.44	1.08	0.78	0.54

The results indicate that for the two concentrations examined Beer's law seems to be valid in the case of methylene blue.

TABLE VII.

Chromic acid.

Conc.		5600Å.	5870Å.	6160Å.	6540Å.
1.416 N	<i>e</i>	0.58	0.27	0.23	0.15
"	<i>e.</i>	0.58	0.27	0.23	0.15
2.833	<i>e</i>	1.44	0.50	0.38	0.25
"	<i>e.</i>	1.16	0.54	0.46	0.30
5.666	<i>e</i>	—	1.38	0.86	0.50
"	<i>e.</i>	—	1.08	0.92	0.60

Beer's law seems to be fairly applicable in the case of chromic acid for the concentrations examined. As in previous cases the related concentrations show better agreement than the concentrations which are widely apart.

TABLE VIII.

Nickel nitrate.

Conc.		4400Å.	4600Å.	4800Å.	5000Å.	5200Å.	5400Å.	5600Å.	5800Å.	6000Å.
0.208 M	<i>e</i>	0.16	0.10	0.06	0.04	0.05	0.05	0.05	0.09	0.16
"	<i>e.</i>	0.16	0.10	0.06	0.04	0.05	0.05	0.05	0.09	0.16
1.04	<i>e</i>	0.82	0.55	0.30	0.30	0.25	0.27	0.27	0.28	0.47
"	<i>e.</i>	0.80	0.50	0.30	0.20	0.25	0.25	0.25	0.45	0.80
2.08	<i>e</i>	1.65	1.20	0.57	0.52	0.55	0.57	0.60	0.96	1.70
"	<i>e.</i>	1.60	1.00	0.60	0.40	0.50	0.50	0.50	0.90	1.60
4.16	<i>e</i>	—	2.45	1.30	1.10	1.17	1.20	1.25	1.95	4.45
"	<i>e.</i>	—	2.00	1.20	0.80	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.80	3.20

Considering the wide range (4·16 *M* to 0·208 *M*) examined the results are fairly in agreement with the Beer's law. If the concentrations 1·04 *M*, 2·00 *M* and 4·16 *M* are alone compared the validity of the law is excellent.

TABLE IX.

Nickel nitrate.

Conc.		6200Å.	6400Å.	6600Å.	7000Å.
0·208 <i>M</i>	<i>e</i>	0·29	0·36	0·40	0·45
"	<i>e.</i>	0·29	0·36	0·40	0·45
1·04	<i>e</i>	—	1·90	2·20	2·45
"	<i>e.</i>	—	1·80	2·00	2·20
2·08	<i>e</i>	3·0	—	—	—
"	<i>e.</i>	2·9	—	—	—
4·16		—	—	—	—
"		—	—	—	—

TABLE X.

Nickel sulphate.

Conc.		4600Å.	4800Å.	5000Å.	5200Å.	5400Å.	5600Å.	5800Å.	6000Å.	6200Å.	6400Å.
0·93 <i>N</i>	<i>e</i>	0·10	0·08	0·05	0·08	0·10	0·15	0·17	0·30	0·55	0·70
2·30	<i>e</i>	0·32	0·17	0·10	0·17	0·20	0·30	0·42	0·70	1·25	1·70
5·28	<i>e</i>	0·90	0·48	0·27	0·40	0·50	0·65	1·05	1·65	2·35	—

These results show that deviation from Beer's law becomes more marked as the concentration differences increase. Nickel salts show high absorption at both ends of the visible spectrum. It will be observed that as these regions are approached, specially at high concentrations, the deviation from Beer's law becomes still enhanced.

TABLE XI.

Nickel chloride.

Conc.		6200Å.	6000Å.	5800Å.	5600Å.	5400Å.	5200Å.	5000Å.	4800Å.
0·926 <i>N</i>	<i>e</i>	0·57	0·36	0·27	0·22	0·18	0·16	0·16	0·23
4·63	<i>e</i>	2·0	1·38	0·88	0·60	0·46	0·40	0·37	0·58
9·26	<i>e</i>	—	2·0	1·36	1·02	0·84	0·77	1·04	2·0

Beer's law completely breaks down in this case. The law fails even when the concentrations 4.63 *N* and 9.26 *N* alone are compared. It seems that nickel chloride behaves in a very similar manner to cupric chloride. It is most likely that complexes of the nature NiCl_3 , NiCl_4 , etc., like CuCl_2 , CuCl_4 are formed in solution.

TABLE XII.

Cobalt chloride.

Conc.		7000Å.	6600Å.	6200Å.	6000Å.	5800Å.	5400Å.	4600Å.	4400Å.
0.183 <i>M</i>	<i>e</i>	0.05	0.07	—	0.08	—	0.55	0.59	0.35
0.915	<i>e</i>	0.32	—	0.46	—	0.73	3.75	3.15	1.6
1.83	<i>e</i>	—	0.82	0.85	1.05	1.70	—	—	3.75

The law does not seem to be applicable in case of cobalt chloride.

All these results point out that merely increase in the degree of ionisation does not affect Beer's law. Thus Beer's law is more or less applicable in the case of potassium dichromate, picric acid, didymium nitrate chromic acid, nickel nitrate and nickel sulphate for the concentrations examined.